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ORGANIZATIONAL MEASURES FOR EVACUATION OF THE POPULATION DURING EMERGENCY EVENTS

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Abstract

The article involves information on the relevance of the topic, research object, purpose, material methodology and organizational work for the resettlement of the population in the period of negative natural disasters and war emergencies in the autonomous republic. First of all, the research reflected negative natural processes, war disasters, severe consequences of technogenic disasters, material damage, as well as an increase in the intensity of many processes in human health and the natural environment.

As a result, several proposals and recommendations were made in order to prevent negative natural processes and war emergencies in the autonomous republic, and to carry out organizational work for the removing of the population.

Keywords: flood, war, engineering, natural, anthropogenic, geographical factors, erosion, environmental assessment

Introduction

The actuality of the paper. In recent years, there has been an increasing trend of negative natural processes and war emergencies around the world. Our autonomous republic is also a mountainous area, so it is necessary to take these issues seriously, because of intensity zone, including natural disasters and war. For the reason that negative natural processes and war disasters develop, they become an integral part of modern society. As the danger of these processes increases, the amount of social and material losses are also rise, depending on their scale and consequences. Social losses are determined primarily by the number of dead and injured (injured, as well as those with physical and mental troubles), while economic losses are determined by direct or indirect material losses. The problem of prevention and elimination of the consequences of emergencies in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic should always be in the focus of attention, and research in this area is suitable.

Object of research. It involves the areas of negative natural and war emergencies in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

The purpose of the study. The research work carried out in the Autonomous Republic consists of taking measures by examining the conduct and implementation of organizational work for the resettlement of the population in the event of adverse natural and war emergencies.

The methodology of the research. Literature on the subject, field materials were collected and work methodology was developed. During the development of the topic, monographs, methodological aids, map materials and work experience of scientists conducting research in foreign countries, including Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan AR at different stages of history were used [2, 5, 6, 7, 9].

Analysis and discussion. As a result of the analysis of the researches, it was determined that the most likely natural disasters in the settlements and the most

important facilities that stopped working during the war were the organized evacuation of workers and employees to safe zones and shelters. The evacuated population must remain in a safe zone during the war and is one of the ways to protect the population from nuclear weapons (during the war). Thus, due to timely evacuation and dilution measures carried out on the instructions of government agencies, it is possible to save the vast majority of the population from possible nuclear strikes (modern conventional means of destruction) and thus minimize the damage.

In cities (settlements) production, education, culture, transport, communication, etc. The resettlement of workers and employees and their family members who are not related to enterprises, who do not work, is also organized on a territorial basis (at the place of residence) and on the principle of production (at the workplace of the head of the family). The evacuation is organized by all CD (civil defense) headquarters and chiefs. Resettlement agencies are being set up to assist them in this area. In peacetime, earthquakes and the collapse of water sources temporarily evacuate people from settlements that may be flooded [4].

Dilution is the organized removal of workers and employees from the enterprises and organizations operating in the area of the probable strong collapse zone in settlements, as well as the most important facilities outside these settlements, and their placement in a safe zone. Workers and employees of such enterprises and organizations work in shifts at facilities (plants, factories) and are taken to a safe zone after work.

The safe zone is the area outside the probable destruction zones of cities (settlements) and the most important facilities divided into groups according to the CD.

The evacuated and sparsely populated population, as well as the Civil Defence forces intended for rescue and emergency response operations, are located in the safe zone. For this purpose, the development of

transport roads, existing communication lines, the creation of the necessary housing stock, utilities, medical, cultural and household facilities, the discovery of facilities suitable for sheltering the population, increasing water sources, etc. Precautions must be taken. A safe zone is sometimes called a safe zone. The conditional line between the safe zone and the probable destruction zone is called the zone boundary (zone boundary).

In this case, the places where the buildings, structures and industrial facilities in the area are destroyed during the floods are considered. People living in such zones are evacuated to a safe zone 4-6 hours before the first wave of floods reaches that zone.

Evacuation and thinning of the population is carried out only on the basis of the decision of government agencies. Evacuation and dilution should be carried out as soon as possible. For this purpose, all action plans are prepared ahead of time. A combined approach should be used to solve such a complex and responsible task. The essence of this method is that all types of transport and pedestrian methods must be used.

First of all, groups transported by vehicles: - Workers and employees of public administration (with their families); -Persons working in important research institutions; -Persons working in the design bureau; - Hospitals; -Personnel of highly trained teams; -People who are unable to walk; Women with children under 1 year.

Those relocated on foot:-Employees and employees of enterprises (with their families); -Organizations that will continue their work in the suburbs; -Organizations that ceased their activities during the war; -Requirements of higher, secondary and technical schools, as well as persons able to walk.

Combined evacuation of the population should be carried out on a territorial-production basis. This means that workers, employees, students and their family members must be registered and transferred to the account of the enterprise where they work and study. Other members of the family who do not work or study are registered and relocated by local housing and communal services. Dilution and resettlement are considered complete after the evacuation of the entire population, except for those working in areas of probable collapse during the war.

A safe zone is a zone that meets all the requirements during the military period. In this zone, the population evacuated from the settlements in danger of collapse is protected, and at the same time, the resting queues of the facilities, which continue their work during the military period, also rest in this zone [8].

The safe zone is chosen for such zones that are excluded from shock waves and light radiation. Such zones should be excluded from the radiation of the settlement. Such zones are determined by the size of the settlement, the population and, most importantly, the power of the nuclear weapon to be used by the enemy. During the war, queues at important facilities rested in the suburbs. In this case, it should be calculated that the time spent on their transportation will not exceed 4-5 hours. For this reason, the camps set up for rest should be close to railways, transport, rivers and sea routes, depending on the conditions. Whenever possible, they are

placed with the families of workers and employees. The basic scheme of evacuation and dilution is still planned and developed in peacetime in enterprises, departments and organizations. The accommodation area is created in a safe zone. Displaced people and MM forces are provided with the necessary tools and materials. This is being developed by the Executive Power (municipalities) in peacetime. Accommodation areas are selected by agreement with the military leadership.

Conclusion. The following results were obtained in our research on the negative natural processes and the state of emergency caused by wars in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

In addition to the severe consequences and material damage caused by negative natural processes and wars, the study examines environmental, socio-economic and other negative events, global climate change and the increase in the intensity of these events, which cause great damage to human health, the environment, the economy and society as a whole. As a result, several proposals and recommendations were made in order to implement organizational, engineering, information technology and systemic measures to prevent and resolve the emergencies caused by negative natural processes and wars in the autonomous republic.

Offers. The main problem of prevention and minimization of the consequences of emergencies in the Autonomous Republic is the implementation of organizational, engineering, information technology and systemic measures to solve it.

Monitoring of earthquakes, floods, droughts, landslides, avalanches, floods, etc. from natural processes forming emergencies, forecasting its probable scale, establishing a system of shore protection devices, informing the population about the situation on roads and their evacuation from possible floodplains, as well as it is necessary to prepare the forces and means involved in the elimination of the consequences of the emergency.

In our war-torn autonomous republic, along with shelters, it is important to take medical, clothing, food and other necessary measures for the resettlement of the population.

In recent years, preventive measures have been taken in this direction in the autonomous republic, repair of shelters under buildings, annual shore protection works in the floodplains of the Araz River, construction of dams in rivers and streams to minimize the risk of floods.

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EVALUATION OF FILTRATION PARAMETERS OF OIL FIELD RESERVES

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ОЦЕНКА ФИЛЬТРАЦИОННЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ ЗАЛЕЖИ НЕФТЯНОГО МЕСТОРОЖДЕНИЯ

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Abstract

The wellbore formation zone is considered the most important element and determines the productivity and efficiency of production wells.

Аннотация

Прискважинная зона пласта считается самым главным элементом и определяет производительность и эффективность эксплуатации добывающих скважин.

Keywords: well, method, pressure, result, coefficient

Ключевые слова: скважина, метод, давления, результат, коэффициент

Процессы фильтрации жидкостей и газов в реальных пластах из-за значительной изменчивости их гидродинамических свойств чрезвычайно сложны. Поэтому для изучения и управления процессами добычи необходима информация не только о начальном состоянии залежи, но и о закономерностях изменения указанных параметров при разработке месторождения.

Прискважинная зона пласта (ПЗП) является важным элементом гидродинамической системы пласт — скважина при разработке нефтяной залежи. Состояние прискважинных зон во многом определяет производительность и эффективность эксплуатации добывающих скважин [1].

Оценка состояния прискважинных зон продуктивных пластов - одна из основных задач, решаемых при обработке данных гидродинамических исследований скважин. Достоверная оценка гидродинамического состояния ПЗП позволяет принимать обоснованные решения по проведению геологических мероприятий, направленных на восстановление и увеличение продуктивности скважин и нефтеотдачи пластов. На практике оценку состояния ПЗП выполняют при обработке индикаторных диаграмм и кривых восстановления давления с использованием различных методов. При этом результаты обработки зачастую не соответствуют фактическому состоянию ПЗП. Определение условий достоверного применения, совершенствование методов обработки КРД и КВД, а также разработка